

AVTOMOBIL DVIGATELINING TIRSAKLI VALIGA ISHLOV BERISHDA NEAR-NET-SHAPE TEXNOLOGIYALI YONDASHUV MODELI

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Annotatsiya

Ushbu maqolada avtomobil dvigatellarining muhim elementi bo'lgan tirsakli valga Near-Net-Shape (NNS) texnologiyalari asosida ishlov berishning texnologik afzalliklari, iqtisodiy samaradorligi hamda ilg'or yondashuvlar ko'rib chiqilgan. Tirsakli val ishlab chiqarishda ishlab chiqarish samaradorligi va sifatini oshirish, material isrofini kamaytirish va energiya sarfini minimallashtirish uchun NNS texnologiyasi asosida yangi ishlov berish modeli ishlab chiqilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: NNS, tirsakli val, issiqlik ishlovi, mexanik ishlov, avtomobil dvigateli, material tejash.

Tirsakli val ichki yonuv dvigatellarining asosiy harakatlanuvchi detallaridan biri bo'lib, u porshenlardan uzatilgan chiziqli harakatni aylanma harakatga aylantirish vazifasini bajaradi. Unga katta dinamik yuklamalar, termik ta'sirlar va ishqalanish kuchlari ta'sir qiladi. Shu sababli, ishlab chiqarishda aniqlik, mustahkamlik va iqtisodiylik muhim rol o'ynaydi. NNS texnologiyalari bu borada samarali echim bo'lib xizmat qiladi.

NNS texnologiyasi detallarni shaklga maksimal yaqin holatda quyish yoki zarb qilish orqali ishlab chiqarishni anglatadi. Bu usulda detal shakli tayyor holatga juda yaqin bo'lib, keyingi mexanik ishlovlar hajmi kamayadi. Ayniqsa tirsakli val kabi murakkab geometriyaga ega detallar uchun bu muhim ahamiyatga ega.

Tirsakli valga NNS texnologiyasi asosida ishlov berish bugungi avtomobilsozlik sanoatining asosiy talablari: aniqlik, bardoshlilik va tejamkorlikni ta'minlashda muhim o'rin tutadi.

Ishlab chiqarish tannarxining kamayishi:

$$C_S = \frac{C_{an'anaviy} - C_{NNS}}{C_{an'anaviy}} \times 100\%$$

Umumlashtirilgan samaradorlik koeffitsiyenti (η^f)

$$\eta^f = \alpha \times \eta_m + \beta \times \left(1 - \frac{T}{T_{an'anaviy}}\right) + \gamma \times \left(1 - \frac{C_{NNS}}{C_{an'anaviy}}\right)$$

α, β, γ — texnologik jarayonga berilgan og'irlik koeffitsiyentlari

An'anaviy ishlab chiqarishda tirsakli val yirik metall blankalardan olinib, ko'p bosqichli mexanik ishlov orqali tayyorlanadi. Bu esa material isrofi, energiya sarfi va vaqtning ortiqcha sarf bo'lishiga olib keladi. Shu muammolarni hal qilishda NNS texnologiyalari muhim echim bo'la oladi.

Xulosa

Ishlab chiqarish, mexanik ishlov bosqichi kamaytiriladi, vaqti qisqaradi, tayyor shaklga yaqinlik tufayli o'lcham aniqligi yuqori, kichik partiyali ishlab chiqarishda moslashuvchanlik, chiqindi va energiya sarfi kamayadi, 20–30% gacha metall sarfi kamayadi, ya'ni NNS texnologiyali yondashuv avtomobilsozlikda, xususan, dvigatel tirsakli vali ishlab chiqarishda yuqori samaradorlik, iqtisodiylik va sifat kafolatlovchi muqobil usul sifatida joriy qilinmoqda. Keng ko'lamli avtomatlashtirish sharoitida bu yondashuv ishlab chiqarish barqarorligini va raqobatbardoshligini oshiradi.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar

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